

Firstly, we thank our colleagues for taking the time to review our Data Management Plan (DMP) and for providing insightful feedback. Their comments have been useful in guiding us towards refining our work to meet the necessary standards.

We acknowledge and address each of the points raised in your review:

1. Description of the Dataset:

- [1.1.3] Are you generating or re-using it : As highlighted by the DMP reviews, it's important to make sources as recognizable and accessible as possible. That's why we've enriched the description by adding the URLs and DOIs of the databases we used as sources.
- [1.1.6] Expected size: We understand the importance of providing a more precise estimate of the expected size of our dataset. Initially, due to the early stages of our project, we could only provide a rough estimate. However, after further progress, we have been able to estimate the size to be approximately 900MB.
- [3.2.1.5] Persistent identifiers: You are correct in pointing out that GitHub does not inherently offer persistent identifier services. While GitHub does provide permalinks to specific file versions, these do not constitute persistent identifiers for datasets. Hence, we have revised our response to accurately reflect this limitation.
- [3.2.2.10] Accessibility duration: We misunderstood this question initially. We intend for our data to remain accessible indefinitely after the project's conclusion.
- [3.3.1] Controlled vocabulary: Our (meta)data indeed utilizes the Dublin Core controlled vocabulary.
- [4.1.3] Responsible individuals and roles: We rectified the lack of clarity stating that the authors have the role of data managers.

2. Description of the Software:

- [1.1.6] Expected size: Unfortunately, the development of the software is still in a phase in which it is not possible to give a more precise estimate of the size, other than it will be in the range of KB.
- [3.2.2.10] Accessibility duration: Similarly to what we stated for the dataset, we intend for our data to remain accessible indefinitely after the project's conclusion.
- [3.3.1] Controlled vocabulary: We will specify the controlled vocabulary used for our software's metadata in the revised DMP.

We appreciate your acknowledgment of our efforts and your overall positive assessment of our DMP. Your suggestion regarding the need for more detailed descriptions is duly noted. We assure you that we will enhance the level of detail in our future publications to provide a more comprehensive explanation, especially where needed.